

HOW TO INCREASE THE UTILITY OF MONITORING INFORMATION FOR THE VARIOUS MANAGEMENT NEEDS

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Abstract

Technical experts and managers from industry, municipal agencies, local, state, and Federal government agencies have participated in six regional workshops on marine pollution monitoring, held during the period between September 1980 and February 1981. Following an assessment of present monitoring practices and discussions of future monitoring strategies, the participants made several recommendations.

This paper details the strategy for implementing the workshop recommendations. The new regional and national monitoring programs are coordinated, and their objectives are directed toward actual management requirements.

Introduction

The status of marine pollution monitoring in the United States was reviewed during a series of regional workshops, conducted jointly by NOAA, EPA and the U.S. Canadian International Joint Commission (in the Great Lakes region) during the fall and winter of 1980-1981. The workshops were part of a number of regional meetings organized by NOAA to develop scientific and management directions for the preparation of the second Federal Plan for Ocean Pollution Research, Development, and Monitoring, Fiscal Years 1981-1985 [1]. This plan is a joint undertaking of all Federal agencies engaged in marine pollution related activities, mandated by the National Ocean Pollution Planning Act of 1978 (P.L. 95-273). While some of the regional meetings emphasized the scientific issues connected to marine pollution research, development, and monitoring, the set of meetings on monitoring stressed the real use and utility of marine pollution monitoring activities from the point of view of the users.

Despite the regional differences in the uses of the ocean, the severity and kind of pollution problems, and the approaches to monitoring, several issues and recommendations emerged that were characteristic to all workshops. These and background on the workshops were summarized in a national report [2]. The workshops revealed that most of the monitoring programs serve only the narrow objectives of

discharge permit compliance, and that they operate independent of each other. Regional focus, regional coordination, and broader goals for monitoring regional ecosystem health for the most part are nonexistent. Similarly, State and Federal programs, with few exceptions, serve only to satisfy the narrow agency mandates with little concern for the overall regional or national needs.

Analyses of the problems and lack of implementation of proposed long-term, nation-wide or major regional monitoring programs, including suggestions of possible new approaches for such, were presented by several authors [3, 4, 5]. It has also been suggested [6] that the requirements for the success of major region-wide or national monitoring programs depends on the fulfillment of certain key conditions: 1) achievable, useful program objectives and products, 2) support of management organizations that need to use the monitoring information, 3) support of the monitoring strategy by the scientific community, 4) legislative support, including definitions of national monitoring objectives and agency roles, and 5) regional and national organizational frameworks to provide focal points and assure cooperation and coordination among the agencies involved.

The purpose of this paper is to go one step farther and outline an implementation strategy, using as a basis, the regional monitoring workshop recommendations. Among these recommendations the actual use of monitoring data and the utility of products to the various levels of management are considered as fundamental criteria for a regional monitor program that could be implemented. Implementation is discussed in connection with required organizational and coordination tasks, and key steps, such as the development of regional monitoring plans, definition of program objectives and products, standardization, data management and quality assurance, and provisions for periodic management and scientific review. Emphasis is placed on improving the quality of the information and usefulness of the numerous monitoring programs in place today, and not on the creation of a major new sampling program. Conditions influencing the schedule of implementation, including resource requirements, are identified.

Organization and Coordination

Any region-wide or national monitoring program must satisfy legislative and regulatory requirements. Based on these requirements, the concerned Federal, state, and local agencies must determine their information needs, and jointly develop a regional (or national) monitoring program that is responsive to those needs.

First, there must be an agreement among the concerned Federal, state, and local agencies and the dischargers on the principle that a unified regional monitoring plan and program can be put together, which, after careful negotiations will result in a program that is reasonable in cost, and meets the regulatory and management needs of all parties involved. Negotiations must be emphasized, because to come up with a unified region-wide monitoring program, compromises will have to be made by all parties involved.

Once this agreement is achieved, an agency or organization must be appointed to serve as focal point for the development of the regional monitoring programs. Organizational tasks of the focal point includes 1) the identification of all agencies conducting marine pollution monitoring programs in the region, 2) identification of the organizations whose programs will contribute to the unified regional program, 3) establishment of a regional management or consultative group, and 4) inventory and update of information about data, location, monitoring frequency and other technical details on the monitoring programs of the region.

Major coordination tasks of the focal point and the management group involves 1) the development of the regional monitoring plan, 2) establishment of a regional communications and information network, 3) data tracking, quality assurance, standardization, and archiving, 4) synthesis and interpretation, and 5) distribution of results.

The objective of the national monitoring program should be the assessment of the well being of this nation's marine waters. This objective is achievable if each regional program will include among its objectives the assessment of the state of health of the region-wide marine environment. The sum of the regional programs then will provide information on the status of the coastal marine environment nation-wide. It has also been recommended that certain types of "standard monitoring measurements" be part of each regional program. These could be standard biological measurements, such as the California mussel watch [7], or measurements on sediment samples collected and analyzed according to standards agreed to by all participants [4]. These standard measurements by the regional programs could form the framework of the national program and, if adopted, will require long-term commitments from all participating agencies.

Because of the need to provide a national assessment of the health of the marine environment, a Federal agency is probably in the best position to provide the services of being a regional and national focus. The monitoring workshop participants referred to NOAA's mandates under the Ocean Dumping Law (P.L. 92-532) and the National Ocean Pollution Planning Act (P.L. 95-273), and to the fact that NOAA has no regulatory responsibilities involving marine discharges, and recommended that NOAA should be the agency to assume the role of the focal point. This recommendation has been adopted by the current Federal Plan. NOAA, in accordance with these recommendations, is working with EPA to lay down the groundwork toward the implementation of a national monitoring strategy.

Regional Monitoring Plan: Objectives, Products, Standardization

The regional monitoring plan should identify the management requirements (in terms of marine pollution) of all participating local, state, and Federal agencies, and the monitoring activities that will be conducted to meet these requirements. Individual program elements as well as the entire regional program should have their objectives and products directed toward the practical needs and operational or other uses of the participating organizations. The plan and the regional program is not intended to encompass every monitoring or monitoring-related activity in the region; some agencies may wish to conduct activities that may be too specialized to their own needs, may be temporary or short term, involve special research, or otherwise unsuitable for the long-term management commitments of the overall regional monitoring program.

The plan will have to be developed under the guidance of the regional management or consultative group (major participants and their scientific consultants selected by all the participants), and should contain detail on the specific responsibilities of the participants under the plan. Monitoring protocols, including standards for collection, sample or data processing, station locations, sampling frequency, data and information flow, data archival and access procedures, and the development and distribution of information products need to be specified. A quality assurance and data management program should be established, and those measurements that are part of the national program should conform to national standards. Without the up-front development and subsequent rigorous adherence to these protocols, any attempt at having a national program comprised of a mosaic of regional activities will be meaningless.

Management and Scientific Review

Many participants of the marine pollution monitoring workshops held a very strong belief that monitoring programs, however carefully they

are established initially, have a tendency to become stagnant. Either they no longer responsive to the original management objectives, their original premise become invalidated, or they are superseded by the advancement of scientific knowledge and new technology. There is a need to find a balance between the long-term commitment to established monitoring tasks, and the valid considerations that argue for their replacement. Managers of existing monitoring programs argued that in any monitoring plan allowances should be made for the termination of monitoring programs that no longer serve a useful purpose, and that faster, easier, more cost-effective technologies should be taken advantage of as soon as practicable. To accommodate these concerns, we believe that a management and scientific review of the regional monitoring programs at an interval between three to five years would allow for their timely evaluation and readjustment.

Schedule and Costs

There are two aspects to the schedule of implementation: perceived need or urgency, and cost. Several participants at the Gulf of Mexico monitoring workshop in New Orleans were convinced that the existing programs are sufficient and responsive both to the management needs and the pollution threat of the region. In two other areas, in southern California and in the New York Bight, representatives of local government and municipal discharge agencies have already begun discussing the possibility of the development of a joint Federal/state region-wide monitoring program. For this reason, the first few organizational tasks are the inventory of existing monitoring agencies, program details, and the management needs. Implementation, therefore, will be incremental, and will be influenced strongly by the existing regional activities and the degree of their support. In terms of priorities, perhaps the Great Lakes Region is the highest priority. However, the International Joint Commission (IJC) is already coordinating a joint U.S.-Canadian monitoring plan [9], the Great Lakes International Survey Plan (GLISP), that has many U.S. and Canadian agencies among its participants. The national monitoring program management will need to maintain close contacts with the IJC, and must assure that GLISP results are integrated into the national plan. Other high priority areas include California and the NE Coast. In both regions considerable preparation has already taken place by the local agencies to organize the development of joint Federal, state, and local monitoring programs.

Another aspect of implementation is monetary support. It is difficult to speculate what resources NOAA would need to implement the roles of the regional and national focal points and management of the national monitoring program. Resource requirements would change from one region to another, depending on the

conditions of pollution, program design, and the number of existing programs that could be incorporated or would see an advantage in becoming a part of the unified region-wide and national programs. In addition, the design of the standard national measurement framework, station density and sampling frequency, and number of pollutants analyzed would greatly influence program costs. In the two high priority areas, California and the NE coast, where considerable regional knowledge is available and presumably a large number of existing local, state and Federal programs would be willing to support the proposed monitoring program, we estimate that with a dedicated budget between \$0.5KK and \$1.0KK per region (not counting ship time or other measurement platform development), the program could be implemented. This is a rough estimate, and is totally dependent on the criteria listed above.

It is suffice to say that the implementation of the region-wide and national programs requires dedicated Federal support and a long-term commitment from all contributors. The real value of the program as a predictive tool will be realized only if the program is long enough to allow the detection of gradual, slow trend changes. Efforts must continue to investigate the possibility of joint industry-government cost-sharing programs, and user-fees to secure possible long-term funding. These, as well as other approaches must be pursued if implementation of the long overdue national assessment of the health of our coastal marine waters is to proceed in the near future.

Summary

It has become clear during a nation-wide assessment of the existing monitoring activities that in order to make them more useful for management, a series of coordination, communication, and organizational improvements will have to be made. The results of these improvements will be monitoring programs that are unified regionally and nationally. This paper provides details on an implementation strategy which could result in the desired improvements. We hope that the initial steps of the implementation, the development of dialogue and interaction among the agencies concerned with marine pollution monitoring, will lead eventually to unified, practical, cost-effective, and scientifically defensible regional and national monitoring programs.

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